

Research article**GGE BILOT ANALYSIS FOR YIELD STABILITY AND EXTRA-EARLINESS OF MAIZE HYBRIDS IN SOUTHWEST NIGERIA*****Odiyi, A.C., Fayeun, L. S., Akinyele, B.O. and Mogaji, B. O.**

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Received:

24 April 2024

Accepted for publication:

07 May 2024

Published:

23 May 2024

Keywords:

Extra-early, Stability, Maize hybrid, GGE Biplot

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Abstract

Maize plays a vital role in food security being important as food, feed and industrial crop. However, its production is adversely affected by climate change. Climate resilient varieties are therefore required to cope with this situation. Hence, this study was conducted to evaluate combined earliness and yield stability of eleven maize hybrids across three environments (Akure, Ado-Ekiti and Ondo) in Southwest Nigeria using GGE biplot model during the rainy season of 2023. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete blocks design with three replications at each environment. Results from the GGE Biplot showed significant Genotype-by-Environment Interaction (GEI) for earliness and yield traits, suggesting differential performance of the hybrids in the three environments. Across the environments, H7 and H1 were identified as the earliest hybrids because they had the least days to silking, 53.78 days and 54.33 days respectively while H9 and H1 had the best yield of 2.19 tonnes/hectare and 1.98 tonnes/hectare respectively. Akure was identified as the best environment that can discriminate both earliness and yield traits in maize trials. Based on stability and performance in both earliness and yield, H1 and H7 were the best hybrids. These hybrids can be selected as superior extra hybrids in southwest Nigeria.

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is of significant economic importance in Nigeria, contributing substantially to the global increase in crop production. It serves as a primary staple food for over 300 million Africans and provides more than half of the calories and protein consumed in Eastern and Southern Africa, and one-fifth in West Africa (Olasehinde *et al.*, 2023). The introduction of improved maize varieties has led to a 38.7% increase in yield, enhancing the income of smallholder farmers and serving as a local cash crop (Olasehinde *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, maize has shown potential in combating global food shortages. The crop's versatility extends beyond food, serving as a basic raw material for thousands of industrial products, including alcoholic beverages, pharmaceuticals, food sweeteners, cosmetics, and textiles (Awojoodu, 2022). Therefore,

the importance of maize in Nigeria is multifaceted, spanning from food security to economic development and industrial use.

Maize production is challenging in sub-Saharan Africa because of the unpredicted weather occasioned by climate change. Thus, planting of extra-early maize varieties that can withstand or escape these stresses would be preferred. Extra-early maize varieties attain physiological or harvest maturity in less than 90 days (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2012) and they are preferred to other cereals such as maize and pearl millet because they are more responsive to fertilizer application and attain maturity faster (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2013). Extra-early maize varieties also provide farmers in various agro-ecological zones with the flexibility to plant maize when the rains are delayed as well as when the rainfall

distribution is normal (Oyekunle *et al.*, 2017). Use of drought tolerant extra-early hybrid maize during dry season will assist farmers to minimize length of irrigation and maximize yield. Numerous studies have examined the performance of extra-early hybrids at one location in southwest Nigeria in both the rainy and dry seasons, with positive results (Fayeun *et al.*, 2017; Odiyi, 2018; Olawamide and Fayeun, 2020).

It is important to carry out multi-location trials before varieties are released. Varietal recommendations must be location-specific because of the presence of genotype by environment interaction (GEI). GEI complicates identification of superior cultivars in multilocation trials (Yan and Hunt, 2010). In multilocation trials, some cultivars may be high yielding in some environments and low yielding in other environments. Analysis of the long-term historical climatic data in the rainforest location since 1975 showed that rainfall pattern has no longer been consistent (Fakorede and Akinyemiju, 2003) due to climate change. Unfortunately, drought tolerant and climate resilient maize varieties have not been developed for rainforest zone in Nigeria. This is because maize varietal development is focused on the savanna zones. Thus, maize production in the rainforest agro-ecological zone suffers. One way to minimize this is to develop extra-early hybrid maize that will increase yield and also be climate resilient. Thus, the objective of this study was to evaluate extra-earliness and yield stability of newly developed FUTA extra-early hybrids maize in different rainforest environments using GGE Biplot model.

Materials and methods

This study was conducted at three locations in 2023. These were: (a) the Teaching and Research Farm of the Federal University of Technology, Akure (E1); (b) Teaching and Research Farm of Adeyemi University of Education, Ondo (E2); and (c) Oka farms, Ado-Ekiti (E3). Eleven maize hybrids, comprising four newly developed FUTA hybrids, five hybrids obtained from the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA), and two existing hybrids as local checks were used for the evaluation. At each location, the experiments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications (blocks). The land was ploughed and harrowed. The experimental area was 17 m × 16.5 m (280.5 m²). The land was divided into three blocks. Plot size was two rows of 5 m long and with inter-row spacing of 0.75 m. Two seeds were planted per hill at a spacing of 0.5 m. The field was manually weeded at 3 and 6 weeks after planting (WAP). NPK (20:15:15) fertilizer was applied at 3 WAP and Urea was applied three weeks later. Data were collected on each variety for number of days to 50% silking, field weight and percentage moisture content using appropriate equipment. Grain yield was calculated from field weight and adjusted to 15% moisture content. The data obtained for each character on the basis of sampled plants were averaged and the mean values obtained were subjected to Genotype by Environment interaction analysis using GGE Biplot model (Yan and Hunt, 2010). PBSTAT-GE 3.5 web software was used for the GGE Biplot analysis.

Results

The means of the hybrids across location for number of days to 50% silking and grain yield are presented in Table 1. H7 had the least number of days to silking (53.78 days) followed by H1 (54.33 days). It took H8 56.11 days and H6 55.89 days to attain 50% silking. H9

had the highest yield of 2.19 tonnes per hectare while the two local checks had least yield of 1.00 (H10) and 1.13 (H11) tonnes per hectare. The “which-won-where” pattern of GGE biplot polygon view displaying the genotype main effect plus $G \times E$ interaction effect of the genotypes in three environments for number of days to 50% silking is presented in Figure 1. The polygon drawn for number of days to 50% silking is made of five sides with H2, H7, H5, H11 and H8 on the vertex. Five projecting lines perpendicular to the sides of the polygon from the origin divided the polygon into five sectors. The hybrids and the environments fell into the four sectors. H8, H11 and H5 were late in E1, E2 and E3 respectively. Conversely, H1 and H7 were early.

The “which-won-where” pattern of GGE biplot polygon view displaying the genotype main effect plus $G \times E$ interaction effect of the genotypes in three environments for grain yield performance is presented in Figure 2. The polygon drawn for number of days to silking is made of four sides with H2, H10, H4 and H9 on the vertex. Five projecting lines perpendicular to the sides of the polygon from the origin divided the polygon into five sectors. The hybrids and the environments fell into the four sectors. H9 was best in E1 and E3 while H2 was the best in E2.

The discrimination and representativeness of the three locations for number of days to silking are presented in Figure 3. The biplot accounted for 92.4% of the total variation of the environment centered genotype by environment (GE). E3 (Ado-Ekiti) was the most discriminating because of its long projection while E3 (Ondo) was the least discriminating location. E1 (Akure) formed the smallest angle with the average environment

axis AEA line and thus the most representative of the three locations. E1 (Akure) is the closest to the ideal environments.

The discrimination and representativeness of the three locations for grain yield are presented in Figure 4. The biplot accounted for 73.8% of the total variation of the environment centered genotype by environment (GE). Akure (E1) and Ado-Ekiti (E2) were the most discriminating because of their long projection while E3 (Ondo) was the least discriminating location. E3 (Ondo) formed the smallest angle with the AEA line and thus the most representative of the three locations.

The performance of 11 hybrids of maize in the three environments for number of days to silking is graphically presented in Figure 5. The total principal component (PC) is 92.4%, PC1=57.6% and PC2= 34.8%. H6 is the most stable because it has the shortest projection from line AEA, followed by H7, and H3 while H2, H5, H8 and H4 were the most unstable genotype.

The performance of 11 hybrids of maize in the three environments for grain yield is graphically presented in Figure 6. The total principal component (PC) is 73.8%, PC1=44.4% and PC2= 29.4%. H6 is the most stable because has the shortest projection from line AEA, followed by H10, H11, and H5 while H2, H6, H8 and H9 were the most unstable hybrids.

The ranking of hybrids in each environment for number of days to silking and grain yield are presented in Figures 7 and 8 respectively. H6, H9, H11 and H8 were the closest to ideal genotypes for number of days to silking (Figure 4) while H1, H9, H7 and H8 were the closest to ideal genotypes for grain yield (Figure 4).

Table 1: Mean of the hybrids for number of days to 50% silking and grain yield per hectare

Hybrid	Code	Number of days to silking	Grain yield per hectare (tonne)
FUTA-20EEHW-12	H1	54.33	1.98
TZEE-Y Pop HDT STR	H2	54.78	1.69
2016 TZdEE-W Syn Pop DT STR F2	H3	54.67	1.35
2012 TZEE-W DT STR C5	H4	55.22	1.51
TZEE-W Pop HDT C3 STR C5	H5	54.61	1.43
2013 TZEE-W Pop HDT STR	H6	55.89	1.71
FUTA-21EEHY-01	H7	53.78	1.87
FUTA-22EEHY-01	H8	56.11	1.69
FUTA-21EEHY-05	H9	55.44	2.19
Check 2000 Syn EE W STR	H10	54.44	1.00
Local Check 2009 TZEE-W STR	H11	55.67	1.13
LSD (0.05)		1.65	0.64

Figure 1: “Which-won-where” pattern of GGE biplot polygon view displaying the genotype main effect plus G × E interaction effect of the genotypes in three environments for number of days to 50% silking.

Figure 2: “Which-won-where” pattern of GGE biplot polygon view displaying the genotype main effect plus $G \times E$ interaction effect of the genotypes in three environments for grain yield.

Figure 3: The discrimination and representativeness view of the GGE biplot displays the capacity to discriminate between test environments and their representativeness for number of days to silking

Figure 4: The discrimination and representativeness view of the GGE biplot displays the capacity to discriminate between test environments and their representativeness for grain yield

Figure 5: The GGE biplot showing the performance of each genotype in each environment for number of days to silking

Figure 6: The GGE biplot showing the performance of each genotype in each environment for grain yield

Figure 7: The GGE biplot showing the ranking of genotype in each environment for number of days to silking.

Figure 8: The GGE biplot showing the ranking of genotype in each environment for grain yield

Discussion

This study evaluated the performance of 11 maize hybrids across three environments [Akure (E1), Ado Ekiti (E2) and Ondo (E3)] for earliness and yield using GGE biplot model. The results from the GGE biplot showed that the "which-won-where" patterns, depicted by the GGE biplot polygon views revealed significant genotype-by-environment interaction (Gx E) for both days to silking and grain yield. This indicates that the performance of each hybrid varied across the three environments. This variation might be due to environmental factor differences in the study locations. Similar findings have been reported by Fayeun *et al.*, 2018. Specific hybrids emerged as the best performers in certain environments, for days to silking, H8 was late in E1, H11 was late in E2, and similarly, H5 in E3. Also, for grain yield, H9 performed best in E1 and E3, while H2 dominated in E2. These findings are in line with the established knowledge of Gx E interaction, where

genotypes respond differently to varying environmental conditions (Yan *et al.*, 2000).

The GGE biplot also assessed the discriminating power and representativeness of the test environments. Environments with longer projections on the biplot (E3 for days to silking and E1, E2 for grain yield) were more discriminating, meaning they could effectively differentiate the performance of the hybrids. Conversely, environments with shorter projections (E2 for days to silking and E3 for grain yield) were less discriminating (Yan and Tinker, 2006). Environments closer to the Average Environment Axis (AEA) line were considered more representative of the overall environment (E1 for both days to silking and grain yield). These findings are valuable for selecting appropriate test environments for future breeding programs.

The GGE biplot further facilitated the evaluation of genotype stability across environments. Hybrids with shorter projections from the AEA line were considered

more stable, exhibiting consistent performance across varying environments. For both days to 50% silking and grain yield, H6 emerged as the most stable genotype. This information is crucial for breeders aiming to develop cultivars with broad adaptation.

Finally, the GGE biplot analysis identified genotypes closest to the ideal genotypes for each trait. These ideal genotypes represent the best possible combination of days to silking and grain yield. Hybrids H1 and H7 were earliest hybrids while H1, H9, H7, and H8 displayed the most desirable attributes for grain yield. Therefore, H1 and H7 can be selected as the best hybrids that combine earliness and high grain yield among the evaluated hybrids.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the GGE biplot analysis provided a comprehensive understanding of G x E interaction, genotype stability, and identification of ideal genotypes for days to silking and grain yield in maize. H1 and H7 were identified as the best hybrids. Therefore these hybrids are recommended for the rainforest agro-ecology. Some others along with these can be used as materials in the development of populations or synthetics that are adaptable in the rainforest environment. Akure was identified as the best environment that can discriminate both earliness and yield traits in maize trials. This information is valuable for maize breeders in developing cultivars with superior performance across diverse environments.

Acknowledgement: Funding for this research was provided by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) under the Institutional Based Research Project (Ref no

TETF.DR&D/UNI/AKURE/IBR/2022/VOLII). The authors are grateful for this sponsorship.

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